

Sociology of Engineering: Exploring Female Students Social Quest of Engineering at University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College, Freetown, Sierra Leone

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ABSTRACT:

Sierra Leonean women and undervalued social minority students persevere to be undervalued in science, technology, engineering and mathematics and attain the shallow segment of undergraduate engineering degrees. The sociological researcher engaged a mixed methods research approach predicated in social networks premise to examine when they first contemplate pursuing engineering as a university degree major, who shapes this social commitment, and how the social guidance transpires. Foremost, the sociological researcher inquired one thousand one hundred and eighty six first year undergraduate students entering engineering programs at University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College in Freetown during the commencement of the 2022/2023 pedagogical year of course. Subsequently, the sociological researcher dialogued a down-sample of fifty five women and female students. The inquiry social findings specified that women were further probable than men to contemplate pursuing engineering while in secondary school, prior admission into university, or duration in university alternately contemplating it beforehand in their pedagogy. Metropolitan or western urban students were further probable than rural students to contemplate pursuing engineering after secondary school. Besides, metropolitan and western urban students were further probable than rural students to recognize a school mentor (alternately a household associate) as possessing the ultimate guidance on their engineering academic and vocation resolutions. In social dialogues, women and undervalued social minority students gifted instances of prominent folks who associated their competence and zest for mathematics, science, and problem elucidating to engineering, analyzed the merits of being an engineer, and furnished counsel about engineering pedagogical and vocation trajectories. Inspiring previous contemplation of engineering majors, such as during junior secondary school, may permit women and undervalued social minority female students cadence to grasp essential programs and grasp merit of university rudimentary planning. Correspondingly, Sierra Leonean universities can capture in conscious attempts to recognize women and undervalued social minority female students with engineering curiosities and issue social counsel. Comparable attempts should also involve associating them with other women and undervalued social minority students in engineering. Furthermore, Sierra Leonean universities need assist secondary school and university staffs in offering direction that can impact student's social resolution to proclaim engineering major, that might succor enlist further women and undervalued social minority students into engineering.

Keywords: Sociology, Engineering, Exploring, Social Quest, Freetown.

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INTRODUCTION

Vocation in science, technology, engineering and mathematics disciplines is anticipated to increase by eleven percent between 2023 and 2028, compared to a seven percent increase expected for all occupations [1]. However, women and rural minority students and workers continue to be underrepresented in science, technology, engineering and mathematics fields. Indeed, women and underrepresented social minority students are less likely to declare a science, technology, engineering and mathematics majority, and underrepresented social minority students are less likely to persist in one [2]. This underrepresentation is particularly pronounced in engineering [3]. Meeting the growing demand for science, technology, engineering and mathematics jobs, improving social inequality, and addressing additional concerns to improve society [4] are the main reasons why broadening participation in science, technology, engineering and mathematics is important. Doing so requires innovative strategies to encourage women and underrepresented social minority students to enter undergraduate engineering degree programs and to retain them to graduation; given the climate they face [5]. Understanding the lived experiences of such students is crucial to learning about the influences on their decisions to pursue engineering, an understudied area [6].

In this social inquiry, the researcher examined the critical role of social networks, relationships with social alters (influential individuals), and the knowledge and resources accessible through those relationships in Bourdieu's concept of cultural reproduction [7] in influencing students decisions to pursue engineering as an undergraduate degree major. The literature demonstrates that social networks provide women and underrepresented social minority female students with access to relationships and crucial resources that help them make academic and career decisions and succeed in science, technology, engineering and mathematics higher education [3]. However, women and underrepresented social minority female students may not have sufficient access to necessary and relevant social networks [8] due to their historical exclusion from science, technology, engineering and mathematics fields, which were created to serve metropolitan or urban men in the middle to upper social class [9]. To inform the pivotal initial step in the engineering career that includes declaring an engineering major, the social researcher examine when students from various Sierra Leonean demographic groups first contemplate pursuing an engineering undergraduate major, the people who influenced their decision, and how or the mechanisms through which the social influence occurred.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social networks are most beneficial when comprised of individuals with access to social capital (for instance, extensive knowledge and resources). Typically, parents are students first social alters and source of social capital. For example, parents may supplement their children's public education with informal learning via museum visits, literature, and travel [10]. In addition, children from higher socioeconomic statuses tend to attain higher test scores than those from lower Socio Economic Statuses [11], due to the advantages of their parents accessing postsecondary education conferred upon them and the documented class bias in the design of standardized tests. Moreover, children whose parents attended university and have higher incomes often face fewer structural obstacles and can return to their degrees after disruption at higher rates than those whose parents did not attend university [12]. Parents have been found to promote their children's initial interest in science, technology, engineering and mathematics through actions such as providing affirmations, providing science, technology, engineering and mathematics related games and toys, encouraging school involvement, advocating for placement in appropriate courses, and enrolling them in science, technology, engineering and mathematics programs. [13] highlighted parents role in advising their children and how that influenced their children's decision to pursue engineering major. The researcher found that parents provided instrumental (concrete advice and resources) and expressive (emotional support and encouragement) advice their children leaned on to make their engineering major declaration. The researcher also found that parents, family members, and other social alters such as secondary school teachers provided advice tailored to women and underrepresented social minority students that warned them of the biases and discrimination they would likely experience in their engineering programs. By acting on that advice, women and underrepresented social minority students increased their ability to cope and persist in the first few years of their engineering major.

In addition to information obtained from parents and family members, students acquire knowledge and resources from their social networks comprised of secondary school teachers, counselors, and coaches, which enables them to pursue engineering as a career successfully [14]. Due to social structure, middle class students, primarily those who are in urban centers or have social networks comprised of parents, highly educated friends, teachers, and counselors or advisors, tend to have higher academic achievement, access to elite education, early knowledge about course taking in preparation for University, insider information on how to navigate college successfully, and access to internship and job opportunities than rural students have [15]. Metropolitan students, who are also affected by social structure, may enter their undergraduate engineering programs with less social capital than other students [16] such social capital may be influential in the declaration of engineering major. For instance, [17] found that middle class rural girls had lower status individuals in their social networks and that poor and working class rural girls had smaller social networks. In addition, rural students relied on secondary school teachers, guidance counselors, and leaders as sources of information about university and career readiness rather than family members; thus, their access to resources might be more limited and unsustainable.

MODES

The social researcher employed a partially mixed sequential dominant status design, whereby the quantitative component preceded the qualitative component, both components were weighted equally in addressing the research questions, and mixing occurred after the data analysis stage [18]. The sample comprised only survey respondents with verified enrollment as first year engineering undergraduates in the 2022/2023 academic year of course. The qualitative component involved two rounds of interviews with a subsample of 55 women and underrepresented social minority respondents to the first survey (thirty six of who completed a second interview). The social researcher designed the interview protocol to collect in-depth descriptive data to elucidate responses to survey items. Social capital questions focused on student's relationships with their social alters and how they accessed and activated social capital through these relationships in secondary school and their first year as engineering majors. For instance, students were asked to elaborate on their relationship with social alters they identified in survey one as influencing their decision to pursue an engineering major. In addition, students were asked about the types of advice received from social alters, how they acted on it, and how it influenced their decision to pursue engineering. The interview protocols used "tell-me-more" probes and requested specific instances, encouraging students to give detailed responses [19]. The baseline interview protocol was pilot tested with two engineering undergraduates who provided feedback about the questions before the items were refined and finalized.

Data Collection

The sociological research population consisted of first year undergraduate students in an engineering program in the 2022/2023 academic year of course representing a range of learning contexts at the Faculty of Engineering and Architecture. Respondents constituted the sample for this social inquiry. The social researcher followed a sample for five years as they matriculated through their degree programs, including those who stayed in engineering, switched to another program, or exited the university.

The sample comprised two thousand one hundred and eighty six students (thirty six percent rate response rate). This survey had limited missing data as all of the questions (except the one on tribe, of which only eight students did not complete) were forced response items, requiring students to respond to each question before moving on to the next. Participants were men, and one third were women. About half the sample was urban, with the remainder being rural. Given the overrepresentation of men and metropolitan students in the discipline, this sample is not unexpected.

DATA ANALYSIS

The researcher used binary logistic regression to determine when students first considered pursuing engineering as a college major and who influenced this career decision. Thus, whether or not a

student considers pursuing engineering as a university major is the outcome of interest. Binary logistic regression allows for modeling the consideration (a binary response) as a social function of individual independent variables separately (for instance, gender, tribe or ethnicity, gender intersection). With this technique, these social variables are not required to be normally distributed, linearly related, and have equal variance within each group [20]. Primary constructs in the model included network size (number of alters identified as being influential in a student's career related social decisions) and whether the alter was primary (for example, familial) or secondary (for instance, school based), which may speak to strength of social ties (frequency of ego social alter communication) or the type of advice provided through the social ties [21].

RESULT

Respondents were provided a survey prompt of "I first thought about engineering as a college major" along with the response choices of "in primary school or earlier," "in junior secondary school," "in senior secondary school," "after senior secondary school before enrolling in university," or "after enrolling in university." Most respondents (fifty nine percent) noted that they first considered engineering major in secondary school. Women were less likely than men to consider engineering in Junior Secondary School or, but were more likely to do so in senior secondary school, before university, or in University. Rural students were more likely than metropolitan or urban students to consider engineering after secondary school. Students from other remote chiefdoms were less likely than metropolitan students to consider engineering in junior secondary school. Urban students were more likely than metropolitan students to consider engineering after secondary school.

The social researcher examined variations in student's decisions to pursue engineering based on gender and regional intersection using metropolitan men as the reference category. Rural men, women were more likely than urban men to consider engineering as a university major after secondary school. Metropolitan women were more likely to consider engineering as a University major while in university, and rural women were less likely to consider engineering as a university major in junior secondary school.

To identify the social alters who influenced student's decisions to pursue engineering while they were in secondary school; students were prompted on the survey, "Think back to when you were considering engineering as a college major while in high school or middle school. Indicate the person(s) who influenced your decision-making process at that time in some way." Respondents could select parent or guardian, sibling or other family members, peer or classmate or friend, secondary school teacher, secondary school counselor, social club or organization contact or other (to be specified).

Students more frequently identified familial social alters than school based social alters, eighty six percent and sixty three percent, respectively. Parent or guardian was the most frequently identified familial alter (identified by eighty percent), and teachers were the most frequently identified school based social alter (identified by forty seven percent). Although there was no respondent gender differences in the type of alter identified, there were significant regional differences. Compared to rural students, metropolitan students were more likely to identify a school counselor or club or organization contact, and more likely to identify a sibling, peer, and school counselor as being influential.

Relational Social Encouragement

Interviewees noted that parents or guardians directly connected their aptitude for mathematics and science and their enthusiasm for problem-solving to the engineering profession. First, they encouraged students' pursuit of engineering by explaining what engineers do, providing engineering related materials, and supporting their participation in engineering related activities. For example, a metropolitan woman explained that she did not know what career to pursue but decided on engineering after consistently hearing from her parents and others in her social network: "Oh, you're good at science and math; you should do engineering." Another metropolitan woman reported that her parents connected her enjoyment of mathematics and science to engineering:

My parents actually said that I've always liked math and science. I would take extra math classes earlier, so they suggested (engineering). I looked more into it and we did those career testing things in secondary school, where you do the personality test and what career would fit you. Engineering was actually never on it. So I'm glad they had mentioned, 'you should check this out,' because it was something that I really had never thought of before that.

In general, parents encouraged students to enter a major or career where they could "do what they love" and something "they're good at." Because they had an aptitude for mathematics and science and enjoyed problem-solving, engineering was viewed as a suitable career choice.

Second, parents or guardians supported student's enthusiasm for building and problem-solving by buying those engineering related materials or equipments. Gaining access to these resources allowed students to engage in some of the traits associated with engineers (e.g., curiosity, creativity, and problem solving at an early age), making engineering a viable and exciting career social choice. A metropolitan man in Freetown explained how the engineering material or equipments his parents purchased for him contributed to his decision to pursue engineering:

I think it was my parents who told me about what an engineer does.... I was always playing with toy cars. That was really big in my childhood, and I had a friend who was like me...who liked to build different things...build wired cars and build cool things.... So that's when I first decided that doing something like that, building something would stimulate my interest.

Overall, the researcher found that parents or guardians and teachers were critical sources of knowledge, encouragement, and resources that connected students' enthusiasm for mathematics, science, and problem-solving to engineering, thereby making it an attractive career for them to pursue. Having alters who were engineers, worked with engineers, or with science, technology, engineering, and mathematics knowledge particularly helped students access information supportive of declaring engineering major.

Academic Social Directions

Recognizing their aptitude for mathematics, science skills, and enthusiasm for hands on activities, teachers (primarily those of mathematics, science, and engineering) counseled students about how to pursue a career in engineering, encouraging them to attend college. A rural man at discussed his experiences with his chemistry teacher as he considered going to university.

I was always trying to be the best in the class and what not, and they recognized that. So, they were really big on wanting me to do better. Especially from where I came, you know, not many kids go to college and stuff like that. So...they were a pretty big influence. They were always...pushing me to get work done, apply for scholarships, apply to schools, and make sure my Grade Point Average is up.

Teachers advised students about mathematics, science, and other classes that would prepare them academically to pursue an engineering degree and succeed in college. Teachers encouraged students interested in engineering to take more rigorous and advanced mathematics and science courses, such as physics, while in senior secondary school. Students who benefitted from such advice revealed how they embraced the challenge of advanced courses, thereby improving their academic preparation for engineering programs. For example, a metropolitan woman in Freetown described how her physics teacher influenced her decision on which courses to take and took an interest in her education. She said, "I would talk to him.... I was trying to tell him that I was going to take the easy science class. He's like, 'No.... You take physics.' I took physics and I loved physics. So that kind of got me into the mindset of taking on challenges." A metropolitan woman in Freetown similarly noted that her engineering teacher pushed her to enroll for a second year in his class.

My engineering teacher in secondary school, he was a very no-nonsense guy.... He was very hard on everybody. So when he said that I was doing well and he actually wanted me back for the second year, he was like, 'Are you taking second year? I really want you to come. I really want you to take it.' That's when I was like, 'I must be doing well at it...and since I liked it...this should be what I would do.' So I think really freshman year (of secondary school)...is when I was deciding more and more that I wanted to be (an engineer).

Besides suggestions related to mathematics and science academic preparation, students shared how supportive teachers motivated them to do well in senior secondary school and supported their college preparation. A metropolitan woman in Freetown said: “My chemistry (teacher)...was like one of the best teachers I’ve ever had still to this day. He was so supportive and really wanted us all to succeed, and then also he was just a really good teacher and got the material across.” A Metropolitan man in Freetown also had a supportive teacher:

She would just encourage me to find new information and just learn new stuff. She would present me with problems.... She would send me to teachers’ rooms just to fix their computers, just to see if I could do it. So I was kind of like, well it was me and my friend, but we were kind of like protégés, so we would like just go around and fix everyone’s computers in the school.

A rural woman at western rural followed the example of her supportive teacher:

She was an intern chemistry teacher, then my intern, mathematics teacher, so I knew her for several years. And to me, she seemed very successful and happy with the things she had done, and she thought I’d be good at engineering. You know, when you get encouragement from someone you look up to that really drives you forward.

She explained this teacher’s advice: “‘Work hard, study hard.’ She, of course, knew it was difficult, so...she tried to warn me what I was getting into. I don’t think any secondary pupil is truly prepared for coming into university no matter how many warnings you get.”

Interviewees revealed that teachers supported and encouraged them in a caring manner and as individuals as they traversed the secondary school experience and prepared for university. In addition, teachers were key sources of information about the steps necessary to pursue an engineering career. For example, they advised students to take more rigorous mathematics and science classes. They also provided opportunities for more general academic development and opportunities for students to become familiar with the academic culture of universities. Students reported that they acted on this advice as they progressed through senior secondary school and decided to major in engineering.

DISCUSSION

This sociological inquiry, which focused on students pre-university admission social capital, provides insights about the timing of engineering career decisions, the most influential alters in such decisions, and how this influence occurs among women and underrepresented social minority students. The researcher’s primary findings are that most women and underrepresented social minority students decide to pursue engineering as a university degree major while in secondary school. They identified parents or guardians and teachers as the social alters in their social networks which played critical roles in their decision. These social alters often had engineering or science, technology, engineering and mathematics career knowledge and or took an interest in the students. They provided information about engineering as a potential career, as well as information about opportunities to access various engineering related resources.

Career Decision: Secondary School or Prior

The researcher found that rural underrepresented social minority students are more likely than metropolitan students to decide to pursue engineering after senior secondary school, which can add obstacles to their academic preparation. A student who decides they are interested in engineering in the later years of senior secondary school may have missed opportunities to take the requisite and rigorous mathematics and sciences courses that position them for success in an engineering program. According to [22], students who indicate interest in science, technology, engineering and mathematics as early as the Junior Secondary School are more likely to earn an undergraduate degree in science, technology, engineering and mathematics. Students who show an early interest in Science, technology, engineering and mathematics have more time to seek information and guidance (for instance, information about courses to complete in preparation for university and vocation) and engage in science, technology, engineering and mathematics related activities to narrow down the areas of specific interest they would like to pursue.

Consistent with other studies [23]; the researcher found that survey respondents more often reported that their parents were the most influential social alters in their engineering major declaration. This finding was bolstered by interviewees who explained that parents sparked their initial interest in engineering, but noted that teachers provided important advice about what it takes to be an engineering major in university. This suggests that students with familial alters (particularly those who are not engineers themselves) but without school based alters have less social capital with which to rely on to guide their college matriculation once they decide to pursue engineering as a major. Having less social capital may contribute to a lack of access to the needed academic preparation; knowledge about the university application process, including financial aid; insider knowledge about navigating university experiences successfully; and the inability to achieve their educational and career goals. This finding is important: students without access to school based social alters may have less access to resources these social alters might have provided, which could also negatively affect their later Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics persistence.

Previous research suggests that having less social capital may be more detrimental for rural students [24], particularly rural girls whose social networks are lower status or smaller and who rely on school social alters for information about university. This is particularly important given the academic climate faced by women and underrepresented social minority students generally [25].

[26] concluded that more research is needed to determine regional group differences in university enrollment processes. The researcher attempted to tackle one aspect of this by examining when students decided to pursue engineering major. The inquiry results suggest implications for interventions designed to foster interest in engineering. Most survey respondents indicated that they considered engineering as a major while in senior secondary school. In addition, we found that women and underrepresented social minority survey respondents made decisions about majoring in engineering between secondary school and university enrollment. This suggests that there might be opportunities to influence students' decisions earlier in their academic preparation, including in junior secondary school. For example, it might be essential to examine the type of exposure to engineering, including engineering career options that students receive while in junior secondary school, with particular attention given to the type of exposure women and underrepresented social minority receive at the various stages of their academic preparation (for instance, junior secondary school, senior secondary school, and pre-university experiences).

Secondary School Social Network Significant for Women

According to the network theory of social capital [27], a large network size is associated with access to more information, influence, and resources. The social researcher found that alter type network size differs by gender; with women being more likely to have medium alter type network sizes when compared to men who have large alter type network sizes. This finding is consistent with that of [28], in which women had small, kin-centric networks and men had larger networks with a mix of strong and weak ties. Although we know that gender differences exist by network size, we do not yet know the role that social alter type network size plays in decision making or other science, technology engineering and mathematics related experiences of women compared to men. Men's more robust network sizes may provide them with added resources to succeed in engineering.

Sociological Occurrence

Students learn about engineering and how it relates to their mathematics, science, and problem-solving aptitude from their parents and teachers. Consistent with [23], students in in this inquiry described how their parents took proactive steps to share information about how their aptitude for mathematics and science translated to the pursuit of engineering degrees. Parents also provided resources (for instance, engineering related materials or equipments, opportunities to participate in engineering related activities, such as programs, fairs, workshops) that encouraged their interest in engineering. Access to such resources is essential in awakening and increasing students' interest in engineering. This finding echoes [29] contention that the transmission of social capital occurs when parents share beneficial knowledge and resources to contribute to their children's academic achievement and career success. We found that by merely reinforcing the connection between their mathematics and science aptitude and enthusiasm for problem-solving to engineering, parents or guardians were able to cultivate their children's interest in learning about engineering, which for some resulted in the decision to pursue an of engineering degree.

The social researcher's findings are similar to previous research but diverge from some prior inquiries. For instance, previous work (and the present social inquiry) found that science, technology, engineering and mathematics based teachers, mentors with science, technology, engineering and mathematics knowledge, talented secondary school colleagues, guidance counselors, and family members familiar with science, technology, engineering and mathematics were influential in students declaration of science, technology, engineering and mathematics majors [30]. Consequently, technology, engineering and mathematics based teachers were the most frequently identified social alters in this sociological inquiry, parents were the most frequently mentioned alter, followed by teachers. In this social inquiry, teachers, primarily those in science, technology, engineering and mathematics fields, are valuable in identifying students potential for these fields and providing information about engineering. In addition, they are well-positioned to advise students about career pathways and academic courses needed to prepare for a major in engineering. Teachers also play a vital role in building students' confidence in learning, succeeding, and persevering in advanced mathematics and science classes.

Teacher intervention is particularly beneficial to students with social networks with primary alters that do not include engineers, people who work with engineers, or others with special knowledge of science, technology, engineering and mathematics education pathways. For example, in this social inquiry, rural survey respondents depended on social alters from secondary school more than metropolitan students did. In addition, a rural student networks may include social alters who were not sources of insider engineering knowledge, such as parents. At the same time likely because of robust social capital obtained from their social networks, white and Asian students relied less on school alters.

In sum, the social researcher's finding suggests that it may take the influence of different types of social alters to encourage students to declare engineering as a major. For most students, parents offer crucial experiences that encourage their children's early interest in engineering. This, coupled with school-based alter influence, helps the students learn how be successful in engineering. The social researcher expect that students with familial alters well-versed in how to successfully navigate the engineering pathway from secondary to post-secondary education (for instance, students whose parents are engineers) are advantaged and may not require the additional support of school based social alters. Similarly, students with only school based social alters who also provide expressive support and experiences may be able to mitigate some of the disadvantages that may come from not having certain types of support from familial alters. Therefore, students who lack the combination of these types of support, regardless of who is providing the support, may be impeded in their (expressive and instrumental) declaration of engineering major.

SOCIAL EPILOGUE AND CONCLUSIONS

Parents, secondary school teachers, career counselors, and supportive peers are important allies in broadening participation for women and underrepresented social minority students. Teacher support and encouragement are primary reasons some students pursue engineering and believe they can succeed. Because many students first consider identifying engineering as a potential major while in senior secondary school, science, technology, engineering and mathematics interventions, especially outreach and recruitment efforts designed to encourage student engagement, interest, and retention in engineering, should be implemented as part of their secondary education, perhaps beginning in junior secondary school. Indeed, our findings suggest that engaging parents and teachers in early science, technology, engineering and mathematics related outreach efforts may be meaningful to ensure they have the relevant information needed to identify children with an interest in and aptitude for engineering and support them. In addition, because many women and underrepresented social minority students decide to major in engineering sometime between secondary school and university enrollment, university of Sierra Leone should consider implementing interventions to engage students with undeclared majors and academic potential during this critical period. In addition, targeting rural students in secondary school programs designed to increase interest in engineering may provide these students the opportunity to consider engineering as a university major earlier, before they leave secondary school.

Overall, the inquiry suggests that multipronged approaches involving women and underrepresented minority students and potentially influential social alter (for instance, parents, teachers, and counselors) can enhance efforts to support interest in engineering. In addition, such an effort would represent a collective approach to provide guidance and support, potentially increasing the participation of women and underrepresented minority students in engineering majors. Because women and underrepresented minority scientists may have specific lived experience related to the bias and discrimination they faced in both the university and the workplace, their advice would be particularly valuable to these students as they navigate the discriminatory climate in science, technology, engineering and mathematics fields.

In addition to implications for sociological practice, this inquiry work offers insight into new directions for Sierra Leonean social research. For instance, this inquiry suggests it might be essential to understand how social alter type network size and configuration changes as students transition from middle to high school, from senior secondary school to university, and from university to the workforce in ways that link it to engineering major declaration and degree persistence. In addition, more social research is needed to examine the longitudinal effects of secondary social alters in science, technology, engineering and mathematics programming, including those offered in junior secondary school and primary school, to determine impact on broadening science, technology, engineering and mathematics participation. Finally, work like this social inquiry, considering binary gender and region can be augmented by added intersectional sociological lenses attending to the impact of additional identities, such as Sierra Leonean gender cultural identities (Bangura, 2023). These areas are ripe for investigation by Sierra Leonean social researchers.

REFERENCES

1. MTHE, National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (Final Draft), 2023. Available: <https://www.mthe.gov.sl/PDF/Media/Sierra%20Leone%20NSTI%20Policy.pdf>
2. K. Langin, "New Study Details many ways Scientist from Minority Groups are Disadvantaged in STEM," *Science*, 2022.
3. S. Roy, "A Study on Women and Society in the Light of Education," *Galore International Journal of Applied Sciences and Humanities*, vol. 7, no. 2, 32-36, 2023. DOI: [10.52403/qijash.20230205](https://doi.org/10.52403/qijash.20230205)
4. M. Dressel, "Models of Science and Society: Transcending the Antagonism," *Humanist Soc Sci Commun*, vol. 9, id. 241, 2022. DOI: [10.1057/s41599-022-01261-x](https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01261-x)
5. S. Allmang, V. Rozhenkova, J.W. Khakshi, W. Raza, J. Heymann. "Factors Associated with Educational and Career Aspirations of Young Women and Girls in Sierra Leone," *Development in Practice*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 1051–1062, 2021. DOI: [10.1080/09614524.2021.1937534](https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2021.1937534)
6. UNGEI, Social Norms and Girls Education in Sierra Leone. Insight and Recommendation Report. United Nations Girls Education Initiative, 2023. Available: https://www.ungei.org/sites/default/files/2023-06/GCI%20social%20norms_Sierra%20Leone_full%20report.pdf
7. M. Ndu, "Examining Bourdieus's Concept of Capital, Habitus, and Field in Women's Health Research in Nigeria: A Feminist Perspective," *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 2022. DOI: [10.1177/160940692211367665](https://doi.org/10.1177/160940692211367665)
8. H. Wao, G. Kersaint, C.A.S. Smith, R. Campbell-Montalvo, E. Puccia, J. Skvoretz, J.P. Martin, R. Lee, G. MacDonald, "Examining How Social Networks Influence Women and Underrepresented Minority Students Pursuit of Engineering in University: When, Who, and How?" *International Journal of STEM Education*, vol.10, id. 25, 2023. DOI: [10.1186/s40594-023-04415-w](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-023-04415-w)
9. P. Meiksins, "Women in Engineering: Analyzing 20 Years of Social Science Literature," *Swe*, 2022.
10. N. Ahmadi, "The Relationship Between Parents Social Capital and Psychological; Health Among Children and Adolescents," *Research Square*, 2022.

11. R. Kaestner, L. Faundez, "Wealth at Birth and its Effects on Child Academic Achievement," 2023. DOI: [10.21203/RE.3.RS-3235776/V1](https://doi.org/10.21203/RE.3.RS-3235776/V1)
12. J. Dickinson, P.J. Leman, M.J. Easterbrook, "Children's Developing Understanding of Economic Inequality and their Place within it," *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 81-98, 2023. DOI: [10.1111/bjdp.12446](https://doi.org/10.1111/bjdp.12446)
13. C.A. Rosu, "Parental Counselling and Its Effects on the Formation of the Child's Personality," *Revista RomNEAS CA Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2021. DOI: [10.18662/rrem/13.1Sup1/383](https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/13.1Sup1/383)
14. S. Freire, C. Rocadas, J. Pipa, C. Aguiar, "Classroom Social Networks, Students Peer Related Social Experiences and Sense of Belonging: The Specific Case of Students with SEN," *British Educational Research Journal*, 2024. DOI: [10.1002/berj.3989](https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3989)
15. R.M. Wood, "A Review of Education Differences in Urban and Rural Areas," *International Research Journal Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp.1-3, 2023. DOI: [10.14303/2141-5161.2023.254](https://doi.org/10.14303/2141-5161.2023.254)
16. M. Amerian, "Identifying the Impact of Social Capital on Quality of Urban Life (Evidence from Iran)," *Social Indicators Research*, vol. 171, pp. 921-936, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s11205-023-03287-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-023-03287-3)
17. S.E. Crann, "Small Town Girls" and Country Girls," *Examining the Plurality of Feminine Rural Subjectivity*, vol. 31, no. 4, 2021. DOI: [10.1177/0959353521989526](https://doi.org/10.1177/0959353521989526)
18. E. Baroga, G.J. Metanguihan, "A Practical Guide to Writing Quantitative and Qualitative Research Questions and Hypothesis in Scholarly Articles," *J Keorean Med Sci*, vol. 37, no. 16, id. e121, 2022. DOI: [10.3346/jkms.2023.37.e121](https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2023.37.e121)
19. F. Kontogiani, L. Hope, P.J. Taylor, A. Vrij, F. Gabbert, "Tell me more about this...": An Examination of the Efficacy of Follow Up Open Questions Following an Account," *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 927-983. DOI: [10.1002/acp.3675](https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3675)
20. S. Bashiru, A. Ibrahim, A. Isa, I. Itopa, "Binary Logistic Regression Model With Application in Students G.PA," *Performance*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 2811-2881, 2022. DOI: [10.55639/607mlkij](https://doi.org/10.55639/607mlkij)
21. D.J. Snape, "Primary – Secondary School Transition Experiences and Factors Associated with Differences in these Experiences: Analysis of the Longitudinal Growing Up in Scotland Dataset," *Review of Education*, vol. 11, no. 3, id. e344, 2023. DOI: [10.1002/rev3.3444](https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3444)
22. B. Habig, P. Gupta, "Authentic STEM Research, Practices of Science, and Interest Development in an Informal Science Education Program," *International Journal of STEM Education*, vol. 8, no. 57, 2021. DOI: [10.1186/s40594-021-00314-y](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-021-00314-y)
23. B. Valentine, "An Analysis of Parental Influence on Career Choice and Success," *Canadian Journal of Family and Youth*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 133-138, 2023. DOI: [10.29173/cjfy29925](https://doi.org/10.29173/cjfy29925)
24. E. Tohani, "Utilization of Social Capital on the Rural Community Entrepreneurship Education," *Journal of Entrepreneurial Education*, vol. 23, no. 1, 2020.
25. D.M. Oliver, "Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis," Sage, vol. 45, no. 4, 2021. DOI: [10.3102/01623737221143133](https://doi.org/10.3102/01623737221143133). <https://journals.sagepub>
26. A.J. Kposowa, "Gender Disparities in Educational Enrollment and Attainment in Sierra Leone," In book *Overcoming Challenges and Barriers for Women in Business Education* (pp.144-161), 2021. DOI: [10.4018/978-1-7998-3814-2ch008](https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-3814-2ch008)
27. N. Vonnelich, "Social Relations, Social Capital, and Social Networks: A Conceptual Classification," In Klärner, A et al (eds) *Social Networks and Health Inequalities*. Springer, Cham, 2022. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-97722-1_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-97722-1_2)
28. M. Veenman, L.H.C. Janssen, L.A.E.M. van Houtum, M.C.M. Wever, B. Verkuil, S. Epskamp, E.I. Fried, B.M. Elzinga. "A Network Study of Family Affect Systems in Daily Life." *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 371–405, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/00273171.2023.2283632](https://doi.org/10.1080/00273171.2023.2283632)

29. A. Gemar, "Parental Status Connection and Social Network Variety in Adulthood," *Societies*, vol. 14, no. 2, id. 26, 2024. DOI: [10.3390/soc14020026](https://doi.org/10.3390/soc14020026)
30. B. Pepin, R. Biehler, G. Gueudet, "Mathematics in Engineering Education: A Review of the Recent Literature with a View towards Innovative Practices," *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 163-188, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s40753-021-00139-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40753-021-00139-8)

